

A mild and efficient cleavage of oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones using aqueous solution of zinc tetrafluoroborate

Adinath Majee*, Shrishnu Kumar Kundu and Samimul Islam

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235, West Bengal, India
E-mail : adinathm@yahoo.com Fax : 91-3463-262728

Manuscript received 24 March 2006, revised 21 August 2006, accepted 14 March 2007

Abstract : Oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones are oxidized to the corresponding carbonyl compounds in good yields using aqueous solution of zinc tetrafluoroborate.

Keywords : Oximes, hydrazones, semicarbazones, zinc tetrafluoroborate.

Oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones are extensively used as protecting groups in multisteps organic synthesis¹. Their synthesis from noncarbonyl compounds provides an alternative route to carbonyl compounds². For a protecting group to be effective, mild and efficient, methods for their deprotection is very important. Several methods have been developed from time to time for deprotection of oximes³, hydrazones⁴ and semicarbazones⁵ using dif-

Scheme 1

ferent reagents. Many of the method describe the deoxygenation of aldoximes which gives low yields for over oxidation. Some of these reagents require strong acidic or alkaline medium, difficulties in the isolation of the products, expensive reagents and potential cause for explosions during preparations, complex reaction procedure, high temperature, longer reaction time. Most of the methods available in the literature describe regeneration of oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones individually. Very recently, a method for the regeneration of carbonyl compounds from oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones has been developed using SiBr₄/wet silica gel as catalyst and carbon tetrachloride as solvent but this CCl₄ is toxic and SiBr₄ being expensive⁶.

Results and discussion

We have reported zinc tetrafluoroborate is a useful catalyst for thioacetalization of carbonyl compounds and

tetrahydropyranlation/depyranlation of alcohols and phenols⁷ which encourage us to use this reagent for deprotection of oxime, hydrazones and semicarbazones.

Table 1. Deprotection of oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones

Entry	Substrate	Time (min)	Product	Yield (%) ^a
1	PhCH=NOH	40	PhCHO	85
2		50		80
3		70		90
4		40		80
5		40		85
6		35		87
7		30		89
8		30		85
9		35		90
10		30		85
11		30		90
12		20		85
13		15		85

^aYields are pure isolated product, characterised by IR, ¹H NMR.

In a typical reaction, a mixture of oximes/hydrazones/semicarbazones (1 mmol), $Zn(BF_4)_2$ (40% aqueous solution), 2 mmol in CH_2Cl_2 (3 ml) were refluxed. After completion of the reaction (TLC), the product was isolated by extraction with dichloromethane. A wide range of aromatic oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones were converted to the corresponding aldehydes and ketones. There was no evidence for the formation of any other side-products. The reaction conditions were same for oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones. Cyclohexanone oxime and semicarbazone (entry 8 and 13) were also converted to cyclohexanone under this condition.

We have found that oximes of acetophenone and benzophenone (entry 2 and 3) were deprotected in good yields under identical reaction conditions. At room temperature by simple stirring the reactions are very sluggish. The oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones were prepared and characterized by adopting standard literature procedure and from spectral data⁸. In conclusion we believe that our procedure is a useful addition to the array of deprotection of oximes, phenylhydrazones and semicarbazones.

Experimental

In a typical procedure for the deprotection of oximes, a mixture of benzophenone oxime (5 mmol, 0.985 g), $Zn(BF_4)_2$ in water (40%) (2.37 ml, 10 mmol), in CH_2Cl_2 (15 ml) was refluxed for 70 min as indicated in the Table 1. After completion of the reaction (TLC), the reaction mixture was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (20 ml). The reaction mixture was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml) and water (20 ml). The organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated. The crude product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluted by hexane-ethyl acetate : 9 : 1) to furnish the product in 90% yield (0.774 g).

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to the Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati and DST-FIST programme.

References

1. T. W. Green and P. G. M. Wuts, "Protective Groups in Organic Synthesis", 3rd ed., Wiley, New York, 1999.
2. G. W. Kabalka, R. D. Pace and P. P. Wadgaonkar, *Synth. Commun.*, 1990, **20**, 2453; D. H. R. Barton, J. M. Beaton, L. E. Geller and M. M. Pechet, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4076; 1961, **83**, 4083.
3. A. Khazaei and R. G. Vaghei, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 3073; R. Hosseinzadeh, M. Tajbakhsh and M. V. Niaki, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 9413 and ref. cited therein; J. Drabowicz, *Synthesis*, 1980, 125; J. M. Aizpurua, M. Juaristi, B. Lecea and C. Palomo, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, **41**, 2903; D. H. R. Barton, D. J. Lester and S. V. Ley, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1997, 445; D. S. Bose and P. Srinivas, *Synlett*, 1998, 977; S. D. Ayhan, C. Tanyeli and E. Altinel, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 7267; D. S. Bose and A. Venkatnarsaiah, *Synth. Commun.*, 1999, **29**, 937.
4. S. S. Das, U. Nath and P. Das, *J. Chemistry : An Indian Journal*, 2004, **1**, 471 and ref. cited therein; P. Laszlo and E. Polla, *Synthesis*, 1985, 439; M. Curini, O. Rosati, E. Pisani and U. Costantino, *Synlett*, 1996, 333; B. C. Ranu and D. C. Sarkar, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 878; T. L. Ho and C. M. Wong, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, **39**, 3453; E. C. Taylor, A. McKillop, J. D. Hunt and Naylor, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 4918.
5. R. S. Varma and H. M. Meshram, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 7973.
6. S. K. De, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 9055.
7. S. Islam, A. Majee, T. Mondal and A. T. Khan, *Synth. Commun.*, 2004, **34**, 2911; 2005, **35**, 1789.
8. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., ELBS, Longman, 1975.